

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR ADULT LEARNERS

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Abstract: *In close connection with the fact that globalization has significantly increased over the past few decades, more and more adults of various nationalities are turning to English tutors in order to find employment abroad, communicate more effectively at work, go on international trips, or simply to take advantage of various social situations. In each of these scenarios, the English language learners are extremely driven to study the relevant material. Using both theoretical and empirical information, the study will analyze the cognitive, attitudinal, behavioral, and methodological traits that adult English learners in the modern world exhibit. The ultimate goal of this essay is to reach findings that are applicable to English teachers working to prepare individuals for a variety of circumstances that call for proficiency in a foreign language.*

Keywords: *language acquisition, experiential learning, teaching methodology, standardized examinations, curriculum.*

Introduction

Recent years have seen the emergence of language teaching as a stand-alone professional subject with distinctive concept approaches that provide a systematic teaching methodology for acquiring language theories and practices. The idea of applied linguistics, with its pertinent formulation and methodology, comprises language acquisition. In the same classroom, adult learners can interpret strategies and procedures used in language education in a variety of ways (Smith, 2007). Adult non-native English speakers differ from other adults in their use of the language. They include asylum seekers and immigrants with a range of intellect and cognitive abilities. As immigration patterns continue to change, adult learners are a complex and varied group.

Adults who are studying English as a second language are required to apply best practices when instructing and teaching. The interests and talents of the adult students from various parts of the world should be taken into consideration while developing the curriculum (Berlin, 2005). The

subject matter should similarly represent the finest methods and techniques for teaching languages in a challenging setting.

Differentiated instruction is a flexible method of teaching that considers the various learning styles and aptitudes of the pupils. As a result, students are exposed to a variety of concepts and knowledge synthesis techniques. This form of training uses a variety of strategies that are equally applicable to all pupils in the same classroom.

Differentiated education requires teachers to be adaptable in their curriculum material and instructional strategies in order to meet the needs and abilities of their pupils (Purmensky, 2009).

Concepts, principles, and abilities that assist the learning process make up the instruction's content. The language curriculum's rules and resources should be available to students, since they serve as a guide for examining and explaining the learning process.

The learning process's goals and objectives are subsequently established. The goal of differentiated teaching is to specifically match each student's job in the classroom with one of the learning objectives. The learning objectives are incrementally evaluated on standardized examinations in order to progress to a higher level of skill acquisition (Smoke, 2008).

Since each learner has a unique set of talents and abilities, the teacher adjusts differentiated teaching to make sure that everyone in the class is aware of key ideas and concepts. This makes it possible to balance the classroom before beginning group projects and discussions.

When teaching, a step-by-step approach is used together with ongoing evaluation methods to direct pupils toward meeting learning objectives. In accordance with the student profile and curriculum requirements, assessments are completed both before and throughout the learning process.

Teamwork in learning is encouraged when adult students participate in a project that interests them. The students choose a shared project and provide pertinent answers to the material. Through questions that advance progressive education, project-based learning considerably enhances adult literacy activities from a collective perspective (Miller & Beckett, 2006).

The functional setting in which project-based learning takes place adopts the K-12 teaching methodology and adult learning's participatory education. This is crucial for adult learners who have diverse potentials and interests while learning a second language. Although projects come from

many sectors, they should be in line with the shared interests of the adult team.

Adult learners' progress in learning a second language is gauged by how well they individually complete their tasks. In the teaching of languages, teacher instructions are created on a student-to-student basis. This is done in recognition of the disparities among students learning a second language.

Since the instructor directs each student in accordance with responsibilities given to them, they are the point of reference in the classroom. Individual performance is taken into account during the student and teacher's following coaching and review (Nunan & Richards, 2000).

The instructor is thus in a position to pinpoint each student's issues in order to provide additional support. The intricacy of the curriculum and the classroom are taken into account in this more detailed teaching methodology.

The curriculum is being developed by the instructor and student with a focus on the evaluation of the student's needs in relation to society at large. Students and teachers work together continuously to develop the classes and curriculum's subject matter.

Instead of being a solely academic module, the curriculum for second language acquisition takes into account the requirements of the learners. An integrated module takes into account the difference in learners' skills and reading levels and compares the results to standardized test scores (Brockett & Merriam, 2007).

The instructor outlines the requirements of the educational program and the benchmark exams that relate to adult learners' learning of second languages.

Lesson plans are learner-centered and content-based. The curriculum serves as the benchmark for assessing pertinent instructional strategies that align best with learners' requirements in various circumstances. The backgrounds and talents of learners vary, as do their literacy levels.

The paradigm of second language acquisition, on the other hand, takes into account students' capacity to combine ideas, concepts, and principles from the curriculum. The topic is presented in the adult class using instructions that are appropriate for the learners' ability based on an evaluation of their requirements (Purmensky, 2009).

Learning generally aims to increase the informational knowledge base. This necessitates that the data be retained for later use or otherwise

remembered (Edelsky, 2006). Learners should be empowered to solve their daily challenges by utilizing the knowledge and skills they have learned during the learning process.

People naturally possess the capacity to learn from their experiences. Therefore, it investigates a strategy for learning from experiences to gather knowledge. The information is then gained and changed to address both personal issues and environmental concerns. In a continual process called experiential learning, the experience is combined with theory, reflection, and possible solutions.

The foundation of experiential learning is the idea that people learn best from their own experiences. According to this view, people's behaviors are more significant than what they have been taught. Therefore, it uses a rewarding learning process so that students may prepare themselves for problems in the best way possible. Additionally, it gives people the tools they need to develop their creativity and originality.

Therefore, direct experience and outside observation form the foundation of experiential learning theory. Reflection is essential to experience learning. It serves as a bridge between practical experiences and theoretical ideas. With the intention of learning from one another, participants in the learning process are given the chance to engage with one another (Hedgcock & Ferris, 2005).

Conclusion

The process of teaching English to adult learners seems to have the potential to be highly intriguing and gratifying, notwithstanding any potential challenges. The drive, tenacity, and life experience of these students may greatly enhance the learning environment. In adult education settings, educators must undoubtedly be more adaptable and responsive. Only by fostering an environment where people feel emotionally secure and providing them with the kind of education they want can teachers truly help their pupils succeed in their academic endeavors.

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